

Investigating the Trends of Climate Change Parameters in Mountainous Areas of Afghanistan

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Abstract:

Climate change poses significant challenges to Afghanistan, a country highly vulnerable due to its geographical features and socio-economic conditions. The mountainous regions of Afghanistan, such as the Hindu Kush, play a critical role in the country's water resources, agriculture, and ecosystem services, making them a key area for studying climate impacts. This research investigates trends in major climate change parameters—temperature and precipitation—in Afghanistan's mountainous areas over recent decades. Using historical climate data, the study examines long-term

trends in temperature rise and changes in variation in precipitation. This study examined maximum and minimum temperatures and precipitation trends of climate indices in the Daykundi province of Afghanistan from 1986 to 2019. We analyzed eight sites, and each station calculated minimum, maximum, and DTR temperature variability and precipitation trends, as well as positive and negative trends. The linear regression trend was utilized to find out notable trends. The findings of the study showed maximum and minimum temperatures were observed to have an upward trend significantly nationwide. The minimum temperature has been raised more than the maximum temperature, resulting in a remarkably decreased diurnal temperature range (DTR). Precipitation indices of climate change were detected by high fluctuation during 1986-2019. Positive precipitation trends happened in all study sites except for the Kajarn district. The mean annual precipitation had upward trends with an extensive range of scattering. During the study period, the Kajran district experienced a precipitation reduction of -0.48 mm per annum.

Keywords: *Climate indices, Temperature, Precipitation, DTR, Trends.*

Introduction

Climate parameters, which are used to distinguish the condition of the climate system and the perception of different climate mechanisms, have been developed based on climate variability. The spatial-temporal of diverse climate parameters is also defined by the climate condition of the study site (Baltas, 2007; Deniz et al., 2011). Climate trend analysis finds out which mean surface temperature has risen by

0.3°C to 0.6°C globally since the last decades of the 19th century and 0.2°C to 0.3°C over the last four decades (Easterling et al., 2001). Recent studies have indicated that minimum temperatures have rarely risen at a higher rate than maximum temperatures, resulting in a decline in diurnal temperature in some parts of the globe. A slight positive precipitation trend has been recorded globally, almost 1% over land during the 20th century, with a more significant rise, especially in the cold season in the high

latitude of the Northern Hemisphere. The spatial-temporal trend has considerably happened over the last century, and trends of warming, enhanced precipitation, and decreased diurnal temperature range (DTR) have not been alike globally. For instance, in the mid-latitudes of the Northern Hemisphere, continents have been showing warming in winter and spring, whole year cooling in the northwest North Atlantic, and mid-latitude over the North Pacific in the last 40 years (Nicholls et al., 2001). The results of studies show that the incidence and severity of minimum temperature events have declined dramatically. The maximum temperature trends have increased typically, and excessive precipitation trends have happened in vast areas, especially in the mid and high latitudes (IPCC, 2007). There is a notable compromise among the findings of regional temperature studies, e.g. North America (Vincent & Mekis, 2006), Africa (Mokssit, 2003), Europe (Tank & Können, 2003) and Asia (Klein Tank et al., 2006).

The annual trends for lowest and highest daily minimum and maximum temperatures have risen in a year in the last five decades of the twentieth century in most parts of the world. Substantial reduction in frost days and a remarkable rise in the minimum temperature have occurred (Frich et al., 2002). The intense precipitation trends have been shown to be positive in about 15 per cent of sampled global land areas (Alexander et al., 2006). Climate change trends may be critical for arid and semi-arid regions, i.e. Afghanistan, and they affect floods, drought and heat waves. Afghanistan is landlocked with a semi-arid climate and is most vulnerable due to intense precipitation and natural hazards such as droughts and floods (Rehana et al., 2021; Aliyar et al., 2022b; Aliyar, 2018; Aliyar et al., 2024). Overall, the annual precipitation has increased in Afghanistan's South, South-west, East and Central zones. Rainfall has decreased, and temperatures have risen in all agro-climate zones of Afghanistan (Saboori & Tomer, 2019; Aliyar et al., 2022a;

Aliyar and Esmailnejad, 2022; Esmailnejad and Aliyar, 2023; Aliyar & Esmailnejad, 2021). Climate indices are poorly documented due to insufficient meteorological data during four war decades. Aich et al. (2017) stated, based on the regional climate model (RCM) of the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX)-South Asia, the mean temperature rise from the global level of 1.8°C during 1950-2010. There is uncertainty regarding the data rainfall analyzed for the past change. The precipitation trend from eight different stations in the Kabul river basin showed increasing 4.88-30.42 mm/year. Also, minimum temperatures have remarkably risen from 2000 to 2018 (Aawar et al., 2019). This study will assess the precipitation variation and maximum and minimum temperature trends in Central Afghanistan, especially Daykundi province, based on global data from the National Weather Service of Climate Prediction Center (CPC).

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Daykundi province is in central Afghanistan and is the second-largest province in the Hazarajat region. The province lies at latitude 33.995 N and longitude 66.321 E, and it is bordered by Ghor province in the North, Bamyan province in the northwest, Helmand in the West, Urozgan in the South, Ghazni in the East. Daykundi covers about 17,501 km square and 2.7 per cent of the total area of Afghanistan, which is shown in Fig 1. The land area is covered 80 per cent by the mountains. The province is divided into nine administrative governments, namely: Nili is the capital of Daykundi with an elevation of 1152 m above sea level; Shahrستان, Gizab, Ashtarlay, Khadir, Kiti, Miramor, Sang-e-Takht and Kajran. Climatically, during the long winter season, the temperatures may drop to 16 degrees Celsius; the mean annual precipitation range is 200-250 mm and mainly occurs about 28-35 mm normally during March and April.

Figure 1. Map the Study Areas of Daykundi Province, Afghanistan

It has a population of about 723980 and relies on agriculture as its primary source of income. Around 6 per cent of the land is used for agriculture, and the main crops grown are wheat, barley, potatoes, almonds, and beans. This province is one of the least productive due to barren and inaccessible land with a shortage of water, small landholders, poor soil quality, and the severity of food insecurity.

Data

Climate indices such as daily temperature and precipitation were extracted from the CPC-

NOAA (Climate Prediction Center-National Oceanic Atmosphere Administration) website: <https://psl.noaa.gov/data/gridded/data.cpc.global.temp.html>. The temporal resolution coverage is from 1986 to 2019. The spatial resolution of climate indices is 0.5°×0.5 degrees. The data was obtained from eight sites throughout Daykundi province with specified latitudes and longitudes, as shown in Table 1. The center of each district was selected as the study site.

Table 1. Geographical Coordinates of Research Studies in Daykundi Province

No.	Districts	Study Sites	Latitudes (°)	Longitudes(°)	Elevations (m)
1	Ashtarlay	Band-e-Mazar	34.067	66.293	2686
2	Kajran	Markaz	33.194	65.625	1244
3	Keti	Bazar	33.513	65.676	1459
4	Khadir	Khadir	33.923	65.933	2461
5	Miramor	Tagab	33.814	66.783	2285

6	Nili	Center	33.722	66.144	2009
7	Sang-e-Takht	Paish-Mazar	34.192	66.041	2730
8	Shahristan	Ulqan	33.702	66.563	2183

Analysis Approach

This study estimated the changes in each of the minimum and maximum temperature trends and precipitation extreme statistics by using linear regression.

Linear Regression

One of the simplest methods to calculate the trend of the data is linear regression. The equation of linear regression line is defined by:

$$Y = a + bX \quad (1)$$

Where, X is explanatory variable and Y is the dependent variable, b is the slope of the line and a is the intercept. The slope of regression describes the trend, with positive as increasing and negative decreasing trend. The observed trend is conducted by considering the precipitation and temperatures as dependent variable and time as explanatory variable.

Results and Discussion

Temperature Trend

The driving force of prediction and detection of long-time changes in temperature indices explored climate change analysis. This study analyzed three temperature indices, i.e. maximum temperature, minimum temperature and diurnal temperature, in the entire Daykundi province. The maximum temperature trend has significantly increased in all study sites (Figure 2 - Appendix). Khadir, Miramor, Sang-e-Takht and Shahristan with higher raised maximum temperatures of 2.1 °C, 2.02 °C, 2 °C and 2.1°C, respectively, during thirty-four years and temperature variations are shown in Fig 2. The mean annual minimum temperature variation has increased significantly compared to maximum temperatures. The analysis of minimum temperature shows that the cold season has become warmer, and these areas are more vulnerable due to climate change impacts.

Table 2. The Variation of Maximum, Minimum and Diurnal Temperatures during 1986 to 2019 in Daykundi Province

No.	Sites	Change in Tmax	Change in Tmin	Change in DTR
1	Ashtarlay	1.972	2.6826	-0.7106
2	Kajran	1.3906	2.2712	-0.8806
3	Keti	1.3498	2.635	-1.2852
4	Khadir	2.0128	3.1076	-1.0948
5	Miramor	2.0298	5.8718	-3.842
6	Nili	1.8428	2.6758	-0.833
7	Sang-e-Takht	2.0128	3.1076	-1.0948
8	Shahristan	2.159	2.1692	-0.0102

Data in Table 2 were observed in Miramor with a highly positive trend (5.8 °C) and Khadir and Sang-Takht with (3.1°C) increased minimum temperature. A study of minimum and maximum temperatures was conducted in Thailand, showing that the temperature extremes rose notably on summer days and decreased on cool nights (Masud et al., 2016). The mean annual temperature has risen 0.5-1.5

°C in south Canada, and the minimum temperature is greater than the maximum temperature in the first five decades of the 20th century (Zhang et al., 2000). The findings of the study in the Arab region during the middle of the century agreed with warming trends that indicate warm days and nights, greater extreme temperatures, and lower cold days and nights (Donat et al., 2014). The finding of a study in

Hindu Kush Himalaya over the period of 1961 to 2015 was an accord that indicated a reduction in the number of cold days, cold nights and frost days, and a trend of minimum temperature water higher than maximum temperature significantly (Sun et al., 2017).

temperature range (DTR) is a parameter independent of the interior of climate change. Data shows the mean minimum temperature is not higher than the mean maximum temperature, and the study showed the DTR negative trend in all stations of Daykundi Province. The study's findings in Bangladesh from 1961 to 2008 agree that it showed a downward diurnal temperature trend (DTR) (Shahid et al., 2012). The result of the study shows that the negative trends of DTR depend on the positive trend of cloud cover (Zhou et al., 2009). The study by Jaswal (2010) confirmed that cloud cover causes a reduction of DTR in Bangladesh during pre-monsoon and winter

seasons. The reduction in DTR over 50 years is attributed to the rise of cloud cover (Braganza et al., 2004). Cloud cover influenced the reduction of DTR in the northern and southern hemispheres in summer from 1921 to 2010 (Yong et al., 2017). Also, a reduction in DTR occurred in all of Canada over the twentieth century (Zhang et al., 2000). The minimum precipitation was within the range of 15mm in Kajran and 48mm in Mairamoor in 2018.

Precipitation Trend

The mean annual precipitation in the Daykundi province (Nili) center is nearly 214.5 m. Table 3 shows that the maximum precipitation occurred in 783 mm in 2019 and the minimum precipitation was 20.8mm in 2018. Precipitation trends indicate upward with 5.1mm per year, resulting in high fluctuations of precipitation indices during the study period (Figure 3 - Appendix).

Table 3. Precipitation Trend during 1986-2019 in Daykundi Province

No.	Sites	Mean annual precipitation (mm)	Maximum Precipitation (mm)	Year	Minimum precipitation (mm)	Year	Change in precipitations in year (mm)
1	Ashtarlay	250.9	663	2013	28	2018	8.4807
2	Kajran	146.2	283	1992	15	2018	-0.4864
3	Keti	181	350	2019	20	2018	0.4713
4	Khadir	223.8	449	2019	22	2018	4.3481
5	Mairamoor	262	644	2016	48	2018	10.226
6	Nili	214.5	783	2019	20.8	2018	5.1468
7	Sang-e-Takht	223.8	449	2019	22.2	2018	4.3481
8	Shahristan	214.6	516.7	2019	25.1	2018	5.5052

Precipitation oscillations were extremely befallen in Ashtarlay, Shahristan, Sang-Takhat and Khadir districts in Daykundi province. The Kajran district, with a downward precipitation trend (-0.48 mm per year), was recognized in the study sites. A study by Longobardi et al. (2010) corroborated decreased precipitation in Italy during the last five decades. The study's findings in Pakistan show notably declining precipitation trends in western parts of the Indus River Basin and a remarkable rise in precipitation variation in high mountain ranges (Hartmann & Buchanan, 2014). The downward trend of precipitation

occurred in most Mediterranean regions between 1901 and 2009, and there was a rise in precipitation in northern Africa, Italy, and the Peninsula (Philandras et al., 2011).

Conclusion

Climate indices fluctuated significantly during five decades, affecting nature and living things. Ecosystems and humans can respond to alterations in climate parameters rather than they do the conversion in average parameters. However, the analyzed variation of climate

parameters is momentous for future prediction, especially in the agriculture and water sectors. The study examined climate indices trends in eight selected sites throughout Daykundi province. The variability of climate indices was observed by linear regression. The mean annual maximum, minimum and diurnal temperatures and mean annual precipitation were analyzed for all stations of Daykundi province from 1986 to 2019.

The results of this study mentioned which climate indices variation numerate momentous climate profile of Afghanistan, especially Daykundi province, where temperature trends and precipitation variation have happened during the past decades. The meteorological department needs more data to analyze climate parameters due to climate change. Spatial-temporal data from CPC-NOAA (Climate Prediction Center-National Oceanic Atmosphere Administration) is a way to analyze the climate indices and show the impact of climate change. According to the study's findings, the maximum temperature has increased significantly. Tmax in Khadir, Miramor, Sang-e-Takht and Shahrstan districts show a rise of more than 2°C and these areas are more vulnerable due to climate change. The minimum temperature shows a positive trend compared to the maximum temperature in the whole of Daykundi. Cool days, cool nights, and frost days were less experienced than in previous centuries. The diurnal temperature range (DTR) has been decreased substantially. The reduction of DTR depends on a lower level of Tmax than Tmin during the entire study period, and it highlighted that ongoing warming is a global phenomenon.

Overall, precipitation showed a positive trend with high fluctuation during the study period except for the Kajran districts. The positive trend of precipitation shows a wide range of dispersion. Conversely, the western area of Daykundi province observed a negative precipitation trend with a record of -0.48mm per year from 1986 to 2019.

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Appendix

Figure 2. Precipitation Trends in Daykundi Province over the Period of 1986 to 2019

Figure 3. The Mean Annual of Maximum, Minimum Temperatures and DTR Trends in Dayknundi Province during 1986-2019